

The space-time structure of turbulence for lidar-assisted wind turbine control

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ABSTRACT

Lidar-assisted wind turbine control has been proven to be beneficial for turbine load reduction. It relies on the preview of incoming turbulence provided by a nacelle lidar, which allows the turbine controller to react to the flow disturbances before their impact on the turbine. When assessing its benefits, previous studies mainly use the standard turbulence parameters suggested by the IEC 61400-1 standard and assume Taylor's frozen hypothesis. Based on atmospheric turbulence observations, the parameters of the Mann spectral turbulence model differ significantly from the values recommended in the standard, and they vary, e.g., with atmospheric stability. Also, turbulence evolution from upstream to the rotor position conflicts with the frozen turbulence hypothesis, and its effect on the preview quality by a nacelle lidar still needs quantification. This work presents a simple method to extend the Mann model to account for the temporal evolution of turbulence using a space-time spectral velocity tensor. Under various atmospheric stability conditions, we derive the space-time tensor parameters and evaluate the space-time tensor using data from a five-beam lidar and a meteorological mast, we found good agreement between the space-time tensor and the measurement data. In addition, a numerical method for simulating a four-dimensional (4D) space-time velocity field based on the space-time tensor is presented. In the end, we analyze the importance of including the temporal evolution of turbulence for assessing lidar wind preview quality.

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1. Introduction

Wind turbines usually operate in turbulent wind conditions that are highly stochastic. Conventionally, they only rely on the feedback control strategy, with which they react to the disturbance after this has impacted the turbine. A nacelle lidar can provide a preview of the rotor effective wind speed (REWS) in front of the turbine and allows for a possible feedforward control action [1]. This technology is often referred to as lidar-assisted control (LAC). Until today, several LAC concepts have been presented in the literature [1,2], among them the most promising so far with only slightly increased complexity is the collective pitch feedforward control (CPFF). CPFF has been deployed in commercial projects [3] and is increasingly drawing attention in the wind energy community.

Some key features of nacelle lidar measurements, as shown by Fig. 1, are:

- The number of measuring positions is limited, implying limitations in the estimation of the REWS.
- Lidars measure the line-of-sight (LOS) wind velocity v_{los} , which is the projection of the wind vector onto the lidar beam direction. LOS measurements can be contaminated by lateral and vertical wind components [4], if the beam is not pointing in the longitudinal direction. The misalignment can be caused by the inherent lidar-beam opening angles, the nacelle motion, or the turbine yaw misalignment.
- The measurements collected by a lidar generally correspond to the weighted average of the LOS along the lidar beam [5,6].

Besides, when the nacelle lidar measurement is utilized for control purposes, we need to consider:

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Fig. 1. Typical nacelle lidar measurements over a wind field. The evolved turbulence (more transparent) illustrates the actual rotor disturbance while the upstream turbulence is observed by the lidar. A Gaussian range weighting shape/function is shown for LOS measurements (the LOS speeds along the beam are weight averaged by this function to get lidar LOS measurement).

- (d) Turbulence evolution (usually quantified by the longitudinal coherence) from upstream to rotor positions [7,8]: This phenomenon is shown by the difference between upstream and the evolved turbulence in Fig. 1. There, only the overall eddy shapes remain unchanged but the smaller eddy structures change as time passes.
- (d) The time lag between the lidar measurement and arrival of the disturbance at the rotor needs to be updated continuously for LAC, because it depends on the varying mean wind speed.

Due to these features, it is important to process the lidar measurement signals before it can be utilized by the control system, because not all measured information is correlated with the actual rotor disturbance [9] and the target collective blade pitch angles need to be reached at the correct time.

In practice, the turbine is reacting to the averaged longitudinal wind component over the rotor-swept area that contributes most significantly to the turbine performance. During operation, the REWS can be estimated from turbine signals [4,10], but would be too late to be used for feedforward control [11]. The lidar LOS measurement is firstly used to estimate the longitudinal wind component. Such estimation is often referred to as wind field reconstruction [1]. Then, the lidar estimated REWS is computed by averaging the reconstructed longitudinal velocity components from different measurement positions. By analyzing the coherence between REWS of the turbine to the one provided by the lidar, one can design filters to filter out the uncorrelated information in the lidar estimated REWS and avoid unnecessary control actions [1,9,12]. Afterward, data time-shifting is necessary to ensure the correct timing of the control action [13]. Besides, the coherence study can also be carried out assuming that the turbulence is well described by a certain turbulence model. A correlation between the REWS and the lidar-estimated REWS can be calculated analytically using the

turbulence model, the lidar scanning configuration and probe volume as well as the turbine rotor size.

Several studies have analyzed the coherence between the turbine-based REWS and that estimated by lidar, using the two turbulence models given by the IEC 61400–1 wind turbine design standard [14]; the Mann uniform shear model [15], hereafter referred to as the Mann model, and the Kaimal spectra [16] with an exponential coherence model, hereafter referred to as the Kaimal model. For example, Simley et al. [12] and Schlipf et al. [17] derived the coherence using the Kaimal model. Dong et al. [18] compared the coherence computed using Mann and Kaimal models. In these studies, the turbulence parameters given by the IEC 61400-1 standard were used. Held and Mann [4] also compared the two latter models with measurements from a field experiment that used two commercial lidars and a small size wind turbine.

Some attempts have been made to simulate the effect of wind evolution on LAC. For instance, Laks et al. [19] and Bossanyi [20] unfroze the turbulence by generating another upstream turbulent wind field for lidar measurement simulation. They both used the turbulence parameters from the IEC standard and modeled the longitudinal coherence using the model of Kristensen [21]. Other works focus on verifying turbulence evolution models, such as that of Simley and Pao [7] and de Maré and Mann [22] using large-eddy simulations and that of Schlipf et al. [23], Davoust and von Terzi [24], and Chen et al. [8] using lidar measurements. Some of the previous studies revealed that the exponential longitudinal coherence model proposed by Simley and Pao [7] shows good agreement with the measurements and also that the model parameters vary with turbulence conditions.

The study of the effect on turbine loads of the turbulence parameters suggested by the IEC 61400-1 standard [14] has drawn a lot of attention recently. Dimitrov et al. [25] numerically assessed the turbine loads under different Mann model [15] parameters. They found that site-specific turbulence spectral parameters are important for the design load assessment. The Mann model parameters under different atmospheric stability conditions are investigated and summarized by Peña [26] through measurements from the Østerild wind turbine test station in northern Denmark.

Currently, there are few studies that describe the relationship between turbulence evolution parameters and the standard turbulence model parameters. In this work, we propose a space-time tensor based on the Mann model and eddy lifetime theory, which is able to describe the space-time structure under different atmospheric stability conditions. We also evaluate the proposed model using measurements from a pulsed lidar system and a meteorological mast. The space-time tensor is then used to identify the filter parameters for LAC in various atmospheric stability conditions.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the space-time tensor model, derives the lidar spectral properties, and discusses the lidar wind preview quality. Section 3 validates the derived model using numerical simulation. In Section 4, we evaluate the space-time tensor model under different atmospheric conditions using measurements from a pulsed lidar and a meteorological mast. Further, in Section 5, the lidar preview quality of the REWS is assessed using the space-time tensor. Lastly, Section 6 draws conclusions and proposes future work.

2. Modelling

In this section, we first introduce the space-time tensor capable of describing the space-time structure of turbulence. Then the spectral properties of lidar measurements are discussed. In the end, we show the lidar wind preview quality for turbine control purposes.

2.1. Space-time structure of turbulence

Here, we first introduce the Mann model [15]. Then the extension of the Mann model to consider the temporal evolution of the velocity field is presented. Lastly, we suggest a numerical simulation method to generate stochastic turbulence fields accounting for the temporal evolution.

2.1.1. Mann model

The wind velocity field at a certain time t_0 can be described by $\hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x})$, with the position vector (Cartesian coordinate system) in space $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$. The directions of the velocity components (u, v, w) are assumed in conformity with the coordinate system, as shown by Fig. 1. By applying both Taylor's frozen hypothesis [27] and Reynolds decomposition, the fluctuating part of the turbulence $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x})$ about the mean flow $\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}) = (U, 0, 0)$ is assumed homogeneous. The Fourier coefficients of the velocity field

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{k}, t_0) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t_0) \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (1)$$

is obtained by the three-dimensional (3D) Fourier transform, where $\int d\mathbf{x} \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx dy dz$. Conversely, the velocity field can be obtained from

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \int \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{k}, t_0) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{k}, \quad (2)$$

where $\int d\mathbf{k} \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk_1 dk_2 dk_3$. The spectral tensor is determined by

$$\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') = \langle \hat{u}_i^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0) \hat{u}_j(\mathbf{k}', t_0) \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average, $*$ denotes the complex conjugate, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function and \mathbf{k} (or $\mathbf{k}' = (k_1, k_2, k_3)$) is the wavenumber vector. Homogeneity implies that when $\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{k}'$ then the ensemble average is zero. The indexes $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ stand for the u, v , and w velocity components, respectively.

Based on the spectral tensor, the one-dimensional (along the longitudinal wavenumber k_1) cross-spectra of all velocity components with separations Δy and Δz can be obtained by

$$F_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \int \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) \exp(i(k_2 \Delta y + k_3 \Delta z)) d\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \quad (4)$$

where $\int d\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk_2 dk_3$. Specifically, when $i = j$ and $\Delta y = \Delta z = 0$, the auto-spectrum of one velocity component at one point, usually written as $F_i(k_1)$, is obtained. The magnitude squared coherence¹ between two points in the same $y - z$ plane is often important for turbine loads and can be calculated by [15].

$$\text{coh}_{ij}^2(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \frac{|F_{ij}(k_1, \Delta y, \Delta z)|^2}{F_i(k_1) F_j(k_1)}. \quad (5)$$

The Mann uniform spectral tensor is derived based on the linearized Navier-Stokes equations and rapid distortion theory [28] and the details of the components of the spectral tensor Φ can be found in Ref. [15]. In addition to the wavenumber vector, there are three other parameters in the Mann model. They are:

- $\alpha \epsilon^{2/3}$ [$\text{m}^{4/3} \text{s}^{-2}$]: an inertial subrange energy level constant, composed by the spectral Kolmogorov constant α and the rate of viscous dissipation of specific turbulent kinetic energy ϵ [29]. This constant multiplied onto the spectral tensor is often adjusted to obtain specific turbulence intensity (TI) values.
- L [m]: a length scale describing the size of the eddies containing the most energy [4];
- Γ [-]: non-dimensional constant related to the anisotropy due to the effect of vertical shear in the atmospheric surface layer. When $\Gamma = 0$, turbulence is isotropic [15,29].

Mann [15] uses the eddy lifetime τ to represent the distortion by the vertical shear effect

$$\tau(\mathbf{k}) = \Gamma \left(\frac{dU}{dz} \right)^{-1} (|\mathbf{k}|L)^{-2/3} \left[{}_2F_1 \left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{17}{6}; \frac{3}{4}; -(|\mathbf{k}|L)^{-2} \right) \right]^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

where ${}_2F_1(\cdot)$ is a hypergeometric function and $\frac{dU}{dz}$ is the mean vertical shear. The effect of the eddy lifetime on the spatial structure of turbulence is that the wavenumber k_3 , corresponding to the z -direction, is distorted from its initial shearless state k_{30} and $k_3 = k_{30} - \beta k_1$, where $\beta = \frac{dU}{dz} \tau$ is a non-dimensional distortion factor [15].

2.1.2. Temporal evolution of turbulence

To include the turbulence evolution into the Mann model, we apply the eddy lifetime-based solution proposed by Ropelewski, Tennekes and Panofsky [30,31]. They assumed that the eddies decay exponentially according to the passed time Δt and the lifetime of the eddy $\tau_e(\mathbf{k})$. This means that the probability of an eddy maintaining its original structure after a time Δt is [21,31].

$$P \sim \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_e). \quad (7)$$

Then, with the temporal evolution, the space-time tensor can be written as:

$$\Theta_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t) = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e(\mathbf{k})}\right) \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}), \quad (8)$$

with the definition of Θ as

$$\Theta_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t) \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') = \langle \hat{u}_i^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0) \hat{u}_j(\mathbf{k}', t_0 + \Delta t) \rangle. \quad (9)$$

Here, $\hat{u}_j(\mathbf{k}', t_0 + \Delta t)$ is the Fourier coefficient of the turbulence field at time $t_0 + \Delta t$. We shall clarify that the turbulence field is assumed to travel with a mean reference wind speed U_{ref} . After time Δt , the field moves downstream in the positive x -direction by $U_{\text{ref}} \Delta t$, as shown by Fig. 2 (the parameters b_2 and γ we use in the figure are described later in this section). There, the larger eddy structure remains unchanged, while smaller structures decay after $\Delta t = 5$ s. Stationary turbulence is assumed, which means that the downstream turbulence field is also described by the same spectral tensor Φ .

It is possible to write the cross-spectra containing the turbulence evolution as

$$F_{ij}(k_1, \Delta t, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \int \Theta_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t) \exp(i(k_2 \Delta y + k_3 \Delta z)) d\mathbf{k}_{\perp}, \quad (10)$$

and the coherence as

¹ Note that "coherence" in this paper always refers to as the "magnitude squared coherence".

Fig. 2. The turbulence evolution simulated using the space-time tensor Θ , with the following parameters: $\Delta t = 5$ s, $U_{ref} = 20$ m s⁻¹, $\alpha\epsilon^{2/3} = 0.184$ m^{4/3} s⁻², $L = 49.2$ m, $\Gamma = 3.38$, $b_2 = -2$ (of τ_e), $\gamma = 270.4$ s. The three-dimensional turbulence field is assumed to propagate downstream with the reference mean wind speed U_{ref} and the eddies decaying exponentially.

$$\text{coh}_{ij}^2(k_1, \Delta t, \Delta y, \Delta z) = \frac{|F_{ij}(k_1, \Delta t, \Delta y, \Delta z)|^2}{F_i(k_1)F_j(k_1)}. \quad (11)$$

In practice, we are only able to measure with instruments on a mast or with the lidar, so for deriving spatial series, we shall rely on Taylor's hypothesis [27] to convert the wavenumber to frequency spectra, i.e., $k_1 = 2\pi f/U_{ref}$ [29]. Also, we shall determine the longitudinal coherence between two positions with a separation of Δx using $\Delta t = \Delta x/U_{ref}$.

Mann [15] listed several eddy lifetime expressions, which have in common that

$$\tau(\mathbf{k}) \begin{cases} \propto |\mathbf{k}|^{b_1}, & \text{for } |\mathbf{k}| \rightarrow \infty, \\ \propto |\mathbf{k}|^{b_2}, & \text{for } |\mathbf{k}| \rightarrow 0, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where b_1 and b_2 are two constants standing for the slopes of $\tau(\mathbf{k})$ in logarithmic scale; $b_1 = -2/3, -1, -2$, or $-7/2$, and $b_2 = -2/3$ (based on dimensional analysis in the inertial subrange). Based on Equation (12), we may avoid using the hypergeometric function and use simple interpolation, or alternatively:

$$\tau(\mathbf{k}) = \gamma \left[a(|\mathbf{k}|L)^{b_1} \left((|\mathbf{k}|L)^{10} + 1 \right)^{\frac{b_2 - b_1}{10}} \right], \quad (13)$$

where γ is a constant (to be determined) related to the eddy lifetime and $a = \left[{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{17}{6}; \frac{3}{4}; -1\right) \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is a constant that results in $\tau(\mathbf{k}) \approx a$ when $|\mathbf{k}|L = 1$ and $\gamma = 1$ s. As shown in Fig. 3, Equation (13) forces $\tau(\mathbf{k})$ to follow the slope governed by b_1 when $|\mathbf{k}|L < 1$ and the slope governed by b_2 when $|\mathbf{k}|L > 1$. Equation (13) is more flexible, one can easily adjust the slopes b_1 and b_2 , and it is computationally less demanding than the hypergeometric function. A good approximation to the original Mann model eddy lifetime (Equation (6)) can be obtained from Equation (13) by setting $b_1 = -1$ and $b_2 = -2/3$.

In the following, we use $\tau_e(\mathbf{k})$ for the eddy lifetime (the subscript

Fig. 3. The eddy lifetime by the original Mann model expression ($\Gamma \frac{dU}{dz} = 1$ s) and by the adjustable slope function Equation (13) ($\gamma = 1$ s).

“e” denotes “evolution”) to describe the temporal evolution and to distinguish it from the original eddy lifetime $\tau(\mathbf{k})$ that Mann [15] used to describe the shear effect. It would have been more natural to have only one eddy lifetime, but it is necessary to adjust the eddy lifetime from the original expression to achieve agreement with the coherence from lidar measurements. Both $\tau(\mathbf{k})$ and $\tau_e(\mathbf{k})$ can be calculated using Equation (13).

2.1.3. Numerical simulation of 4D Mann turbulence

The numerical method to simulate a 3D Mann-based turbulence field was presented by Mann [29]. There, the velocity field is generated by the discrete inverse Fourier transform [32].

$$u_i(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) C_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0), \quad (14)$$

where, for each wavenumber vector and time, $C_{ij}(\mathbf{k})$ is a 3 by 3 matrix of coefficients and $g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0)$ is a 3 by 1 vector of independent Gaussian stochastic complex variables with unit variance [29]. Note that the Einstein notation [33] is used in the equations of this paper which means the summation of repeated indices is implied. Since the index $j = 1, 2, 3$ are repeated, they should loop over all possible combinations and the corresponding result of each combination should be summed up ($C_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0) = \sum_{j=1}^3 C_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0)$). $C_{ij}(\mathbf{k})$ is related to the spectral tensor by

$$C_{ik}(\mathbf{k}) C_{jk}^*(\mathbf{k}) \propto \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}), \quad (15)$$

with the index $k = 1, 2, 3$, and * denotes the complex transpose. The ensemble average of the coefficients is

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle C_{ik}(\mathbf{k}) g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0) [C_{jl}(\mathbf{k}) g_l(\mathbf{k}, t_0)]^* \rangle \\ &= C_{ik}(\mathbf{k}) \langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0) g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0) \rangle C_{jl}^*(\mathbf{k}) \\ &= 2C_{ik}(\mathbf{k}) C_{jk}^*(\mathbf{k}) \propto \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

with the index $l = 1, 2, 3$. Note that $\langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0) g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0) \rangle = 2\delta_{kl}$ is the 3 by 3 covariance matrix of the independent complex Gaussian variables with unit variance of the real and the imaginary parts.

With the assumption of stationarity, the turbulence field at time $t_0 + \Delta t$ is calculated using the same deterministic coefficients $C_{ij}(\mathbf{k})$ but different random Gaussian variables, i.e.

$$\mathbf{u}_i(\mathbf{x}, t_0 + \Delta t) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) C_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t), \quad (17)$$

where $g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t)$ may be correlated with $g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0)$. To simulate a 4D Mann turbulence using the space-time tensor discussed above,

we shall satisfy Equation (8) by

$$\langle C_{ik}(\mathbf{k})g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0) [C_{jl}(\mathbf{k})g_l(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t)]^* \rangle \propto \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right) \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}). \quad (18)$$

This can be achieved by assuming that $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{k}, t)$ is a complex Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process [34] and thus obeys

$$g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t) = g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0) \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right) + g_j(\mathbf{k}) \sqrt{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)}, \quad (19)$$

where $g_j(\mathbf{k})$ are complex Gaussian variables independent of $g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_0)$. The proof of Equation (18) is given in Appendix A. With the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process, it is possible to extend the turbulence field to successive points in time using the complex Gaussian variables as calculated by

$$g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_k) = g_j(\mathbf{k}, t_{k-1}) \exp\left(-\frac{t_k - t_{k-1}}{\tau_e}\right) + g_j(\mathbf{k}) \sqrt{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2(t_k - t_{k-1})}{\tau_e}\right)}. \quad (20)$$

At each moment, the 3D field statistics are governed by the Mann spectral tensor [15], as derived in Appendix A. Using this simulation method, a 4D Mann turbulence simulator was programmed in C++ and made available online. To validate the simulation tool, we generate 4D velocity fields, computed the simulated spectra and coherence, and compared them with spectra and coherence from the space-time tensor (see Appendix A for details).

2.2. Spectral properties of the lidar measurements

To evaluate the space-time tensor with measurements, we use a pulsed lidar, which has the advantage of capturing turbulence at various spatial positions. Since the lidar can only measure along the LOS direction, it is necessary to derive the spectral properties from the lidar LOS speed measurement using the space-time tensor.

Consider a lidar that is focused at $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$. The fluctuation part of the lidar LOS measurement at this position can be approximated by [35]

$$v_{\text{los}}(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(s) \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{s}\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{x}) ds, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{n} = (\cos \theta \cos \varphi, \cos \theta \sin \varphi, \sin \theta)$ is a unit vector in the direction of a lidar beam that depends on the azimuth φ and elevation θ angles (see Fig. 4). s is the displacement along the lidar beam

$$v_{\text{los}}(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(s) \mathbf{n} \cdot \int \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{k}) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{s}\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{x})) d\mathbf{k} ds = \int \mathbf{n} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{k}) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(s) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}s) ds d\mathbf{k} = \int \mathbf{n} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{k}) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \hat{\varphi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}) d\mathbf{k}. \quad (25)$$

direction from the focus point $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ and $\varphi(s)$ is the weighting function due to the lidar volume averaging. $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{s}\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{x})$ is the vector of the turbulent wind components at position $(\mathbf{s}\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{x})$. For a pulsed

Fig. 4. The sketch of the five beam Avelid lidar measurement characteristics. Only three measurement gates are shown as examples.

lidar, the weighting function can be approximated as a triangular function [35]:

$$\varphi(s) = \begin{cases} \frac{h_p - |s|}{h_p^2}, & \text{if } |s| < h_p. \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

whose geometry is determined by the half of the length of a rectangular pulse h_p .

For the auto spectrum of the LOS velocity, Mann et al. [35] showed that

$$F_{\text{los}}(k_1) = n_i n_j \int \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) |\hat{\varphi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n})|^2 d\mathbf{k}_\perp, \quad (23)$$

with $\hat{\varphi}(\cdot)$ being the Fourier transform of the weighting function

$$\hat{\varphi}(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(s) \exp(-ivs) ds = \text{sinc}^2\left(v \frac{h_p}{2}\right). \quad (24)$$

The auto-spectrum was investigated by Peña et al. [6] to characterize the turbulence measured by nacelle lidars. Here, we analyze both the auto-spectrum and cross-spectrum between the LOS measurements at two positions. The spatial and temporal coherence of the lidar measurement provides useful information for LAC. Therefore, we further derive the cross-spectrum between the LOS velocities measured by a lidar at two different positions.

Replacing the turbulence field \mathbf{u} in Equation (21) by Equation (2) the LOS can be written as [36]

Consider another measurement position at $\mathbf{x}' = (x', y', z')$ with the unit vector \mathbf{n}' . After applying the Fourier transform in the k_1 direction, the cross-spectrum of the two LOS measurements is then

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\text{loslos}'}(k_1) &= \langle \hat{v}_{\text{los}}(k_1) \hat{v}_{\text{los}'}^*(k_1) \rangle = \left\langle \int \mathbf{n} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{k}) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}) d\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \int \hat{\mathbf{u}}^*(\mathbf{k}') \cdot \mathbf{n}' \exp(-i\mathbf{k}' \cdot \mathbf{x}') \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k}' \cdot \mathbf{n}') d\mathbf{k}'_{\perp} \right\rangle \\
 &= n_i n'_j \int \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x})) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}') d\mathbf{k}_{\perp}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Note that the ensemble average of the product with $\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{k}'$ is zero. To consider the temporal evolution, the spectral tensor should be replaced by the space-time tensor giving

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\text{loslos}'}(k_1) &= n_i n'_j \int \Theta_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x})) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}') \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}) d\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \\
 &= n_i n'_j \int \exp\left(i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}) - \frac{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|}{\tau_e U_{\text{ref}}}\right) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}') \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}) d\mathbf{k}_{\perp}
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

We use the space-time tensor Θ_{ij} as the lidar scans the first position at t_0 and the second position at $t_0 + \Delta t$. It should be mentioned that the weighting function of a pulsed lidar does not change with the focused position, thus the two identical $\hat{\phi}(\cdot)$ functions. The time difference is approximated as $\Delta t = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|/U_{\text{ref}}$, with $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|$ being the longitudinal separation of two measurement positions.

The magnitude squared coherence between LOS measurements is therefore

$$\text{coh}_{\text{loslos}'}^2(k_1) = \frac{|F_{\text{loslos}'}(k_1)|^2}{F_{\text{los}}(k_1) F_{\text{los}'}(k_1)}. \tag{28}$$

2.3. Lidar wind preview quality

This section further investigates the impact of space-time coherence on lidar-assisted control. The REWS experienced by a turbine and the REWS estimated from lidar measurements is first discussed. Then, the auto-spectra of these two signals and their cross-spectrum are presented.

2.3.1. Rotor effective wind speed – REWS

As discussed in Schilpf et al. [1], several definitions of REWS have been proposed. We use the mean longitudinal component integrated over the rotor area:

$$u_{\text{RR}}(x) = \frac{1}{\pi R^2} \int_D u(\mathbf{x}) dy dz, \tag{29}$$

where D denotes the integration over the rotor area defined by the rotor radius R . Following the derivation by Mirzaei et al. [36], the auto-spectrum of the REWS u_{RR} can be calculated using the spectral tensor as

$$S_{\text{RR}}(k_1) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi_{11}(\mathbf{k}) \frac{4J_1^2(\kappa R)}{\kappa^2 R^2} dk_2 dk_3, \tag{30}$$

where $\kappa = \sqrt{k_2^2 + k_3^2}$ and J_1 is the Bessel function of the first kind [4].

2.3.2. Lidar estimated REWS

The lidar estimated REWS is

$$u_{\text{LL}}(x) = \frac{1}{n_b \cos \theta \cos \varphi} \sum_{i=1}^{n_b} v_{\text{los},i}(x), \tag{31}$$

where n_b is total number of lidar beams and $v_{\text{los},i}(x)$ denotes the i th lidar LOS measurement. Here we assume zero v and w components, since they usually have less contribution to the LOS velocity compared to the u component.

The auto-spectrum of the REWS estimated by lidar can be computed from the Mann spectral tensor [15] by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{\text{LL}}(k_1) &= \frac{1}{(n_b \cos \theta \cos \varphi)^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^{n_b} \sum_{l,m=1}^3 \int n_{il} n_{jm} \Phi_{lm}(\mathbf{k}) \\
 &\quad \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}_i) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}_j) d\mathbf{k}_{\perp},
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{n}_i denote the focus position vector and the unit vector of the i th lidar measurement respectively, and n_{il} is the l th element in the unit vector \mathbf{n}_i . Details of the derivation of Equation (32) can be found in Refs. [4,36]. When the temporal evolution of the turbulence field is considered, one just needs to replace Φ_{lm} by $\Theta_{lm}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t)$ in Equation (32). This is necessary when the lidar has a relatively large time delay or longitudinal separation between measurement positions.

2.3.3. The cross-spectrum between rotor and lidar REWS

The cross-spectrum between u_{RR} and u_{LL} is

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{\text{RL}}(k_1) &= \frac{1}{n_b \cos \theta \cos \varphi} \sum_{i=1}^{n_b} \sum_{j=1}^3 \int n_{ij} \Theta_{j1}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t_i) \\
 &\quad \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{n}_i) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}_i - k_1 \Delta x_i) \frac{2J_1(\kappa R)}{\kappa R} d\mathbf{k}_{\perp}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

The cross-spectrum is calculated using the space-time tensor Θ_{j1} , which is the main difference compared to previous derivations [4,36]. Here, Δx_i is the longitudinal separation between the rotor plane and the i th lidar measurement position and $\Delta x_i = x_i - x_R = x_i$, since the rotor plane is often defined at $x_R = 0$ m. Δt_i is the time required for the turbulence field to move from the i th lidar measurement position to the rotor plane, which can be calculated using $\Delta t_i = |\Delta x_i|/U_{\text{ref}}$.

2.3.4. Lidar preview quality

To evaluate the preview quality of lidar measurement, the

coherence between lidar estimated REWS and the turbine-based REWS, i.e.

$$\text{coh}_{\text{RL}}(f) = \frac{|S_{\text{RL}}(f)|^2}{S_{\text{RR}}(f)S_{\text{LL}}(f)}. \quad (34)$$

is often reported [4,12,37]. In addition, in LAC applications, a good indication of how well the lidar predicts the REWS is by the following transfer function [1,38].

$$|G_{\text{RL}}(f)| = \frac{|S_{\text{RL}}(f)|}{S_{\text{LL}}(f)}. \quad (35)$$

By definition, a filter that has the gain $G_{\text{RL}}(f)$ is an optimal Wiener filter [39], as derived by Simley and Pao [38]. The Wiener filter helps to filter out the uncorrelated information from a stochastic process (in our application the u_{LL}) and minimizes the mean square deviation between the filtered u_{LL} and the desired signal (u_{RR}). A large gain at a certain frequency means that less information needs to be damped out before the signal is used. Thus, the gain indicates how much information measured by the lidar is useable for the feedforward control of wind turbines, with a larger area below the transfer function gain leading to a better preview quality.

In principle, if a lidar is able to measure the averaged upstream u component over the rotor area, by using Taylor's frozen hypothesis, we end up with a perfect lidar estimation of REWS and $|S_{\text{RL}}| = S_{\text{RR}} = S_{\text{LL}}$. The transfer function $G_{\text{RL}}(f)$ is therefore one for all frequencies, which is not realistic. With the space-time tensor, it is possible to derive the value of the transfer function gain with turbulence evolution considered. The cross-spectrum of an ideal lidar can be computed by

$$S_{\text{RL,ideal}}(k_1) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Theta_{ij}(\mathbf{k}, \Delta t) \frac{4J_1^2(\kappa R)}{\kappa^2 R^2} dk_2 dk_3, \quad (36)$$

which can be further used to determine the maximum possible transfer function magnitude by Equation (35). Here, Δt is the time required for the turbulence to travel from the lidar-measured upstream plane to the rotor plane.

3. Model validation against simulation

In this section, we perform numerical simulations to cross-validate the space-time tensor model and lidar spectral properties presented in Section 2.

3.1. Simulation setup

A pulsed lidar manufactured by Avent is considered in our simulation. It has five beams pointing towards different directions, as shown by Fig. 4. The elevation and azimuth angles of the beams are summarized in Table 1. Specifically, beam 0 is pointing towards the negative longitudinal direction (x axis). For each beam, the lidar is able to provide data from 10 range gates that are defined by the longitudinal separation (Δx) relative to the lidar position. However,

Table 1
Scan configuration for the Avent lidar system.

number of beams	5
beam azimuth-angles [°]	0, -169.2, 169.2, 169.2, -169.2
beam elevation-angles [°]	0, 10.6, 10.6, -10.6, -10.6
measurement distance	49–281 m (10 gates in total)
full scan time	5.0s
pulse half length	24.75 m

Fig. 5. Lidar LOS measurement spectra (top frame), longitudinal coherence (middle frame), and vertical-lateral coherence (bottom frame) from the numerical simulation (solid lines) and the theory (dashed lines). Model parameters used are $\alpha \epsilon^{2/3} = 0.184 \text{ m}^{4/3} \text{ s}^{-2}$, $L = 49.2 \text{ m}$, $\Gamma = 3.38$, $b_2 = -2$ (of τ_e), and $\gamma = 270.4 \text{ s}$.

only three measurement gates (72, 121 and 235 m) are considered for the analysis. Using these three gates, longitudinal separations of 49, 114, and 163 m are obtained, which are representative to quantify the wind evolution. Also, the lateral and vertical separations from these gates are interesting to analyze for the lateral-vertical coherence.

To simulate the lidar LOS measurements, we generate a 4D turbulence field using the tool introduced in Section 2.1.3. The field has a size of $3 \times 2048 \times 64 \times 64$ grid points, corresponding to the time, and the x , y and z directions, respectively. The lengths in the x , y and z directions are 32768, 384, and 384 m, respectively. The three time moments of the fields are 6.00, 10.08, and 19.58 s. A reference mean wind speed $U_{\text{ref}} = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is assumed, which leads to the longitudinal separations of 49, 114, and 163 m between the three 3D spatial turbulence fields. Each 3D turbulence field at one time moment is used to simulate the LOS measurement at one

range gate and the Taylor's frozen hypothesis is applied for each 3D field to obtain the time series of the lidar LOS simulation. When calculating the LOS time series, Equation 21 is discretized in the LOS direction with s varying from -25 to $+25$ m with steps of 5 m.

To get the ensemble mean spectra, 20 independent 4D turbulence fields with the same properties as discussed previously but with different random number seeds are generated. The LOS measurements are simulated by each 4D field and the spectra are calculated using the Welch's method [40]. The LOS measurements are simulated using the same sampling frequency as the turbulence fields.

3.2. Comparisons between model and simulation

We have chosen a set of Mann turbulence parameters for the validation of the simulations, which represents neutral stability conditions (more details follow in the next Section). Fig. 5 shows the auto-spectra of both the model and the simulations for different LOS measurements. Due to symmetry, results for beam 2 are identical to those of beam 1 and those of beam 4 to those of beam 3. Also, since the auto-spectrum is independent of the measurement gate (because of the assumed homogeneity), only the results from gate 2 are shown. It is clear that the downwards looking beam 3 has much lower variance (area below the spectra) compared to that of the other beams.

Fig. 5-middle compares the model and simulated coherence decay between different gates of beam 0. Beam 0 is pointing towards the longitudinal direction (x axis) so it reflects the coherence decay due to the longitudinal separation or the temporal delay. Gates 1 and 3 have the largest separation (163 m) and over this distance the eddies evolve with a longer time, which results in the lowest coherence. The largest coherences are between gates 1 and 2 because of the smallest separation.

In Fig. 5-bottom, beams 1, 2, and 4 are shown as examples of the decorrelation caused by lateral or vertical separations in both the model and the simulations. Although for the beam pairs 12 and 14 the distances are the same, the coherence for the first pair is much smaller than that of the latter pair. This is because beams 1 and 2 are separated vertically and the spatially correlated v component acts oppositely on beams 1 and 2. Similarly, the spatially correlated w component acts oppositely on beams 1 and 4. However, the larger energy of the v component compared to that of w component causes a larger decorrelation for beams 1 and 2 than that for beams 1 and 4.

Overall, the numerical simulations match the theory. The small

Fig. 6. Overview of the measurement site. The color map shows the digital elevation of the terrain (AMSL: Average Mean Sea Level). Wind turbines are marked by circles. Turbine 4 with the lidar is shown by the red circle. The red triangle is the meteorological mast. Red lines denote the lidar beams.

discrepancies are caused by the nature of the simulations as we use discrete turbulence fields and limited random seed numbers.

4. Model evaluation with measurement data

In this section, we evaluate the space-time tensor model presented in Section 2 using the measurements from a pulsed lidar and a meteorological mast.

4.1. Measurement site

The measurement campaign was performed at the Nørrekær Enge wind farm (see Fig. 6), located in northern Jutland, Denmark. 13 S 2.3 MW-93 wind turbines with a hub height of 81.8 m and a rotor diameter of 92.6 m were installed in a row, which is rotated 73.9° from the north. The wind turbines are numbered sequentially from west to east. On the nacelle of turbine 4, an Avent pulse lidar was installed. A meteorological mast was located 232 m away from turbine 4, at 101.2° from the north. More details of the site can be found in Peña et al. [6].

4.1.1. Instruments

Pulsed lidar: The five-beam Avent pulsed lidar (hereafter known as Avent) was mounted on the nacelle of turbine 4 staring upwards [6]. The beam trajectory is given by Table 1 and displayed in Fig. 4. In total, 10 different ranges (49, 72, 95, 109, 121, 142, 165, 188, 235, and 281 m) were measured simultaneously. For each beam direction, the LOS velocity was recorded every 1 s. Thus, each beam was sampling at 0.2 Hz, **Met mast:** The meteorological mast had a height of 80 m. Cup anemometers (P2546A) were mounted on the heights 80, 78, 57, and 33 m. There was a 3-D sonic anemometer (CSAT3) deployed at the height of 76 m. Besides, two temperature sensors (Pt500 Sensor) were installed at the heights 78 and 2 m.

Turbine data: We use the yaw signal from the SCADA system of turbine 4 as reference for the lidar yaw position relative to the mean wind. And this information is further used to select the wake free sectors (see below).

4.1.2. Data selection

The measurements were recorded from October 27, 2015 to January 7, 2016. Similar to Peña et al. [6], we analyze the data within 10 min intervals. For each 10 min, we apply the following criteria to select the data:

- To avoid wake effects from other turbines, the data are selected only when the turbine yaw signal is within the wake-free directions [6] (89° – 239° as shown by Fig. 6);
- Data, where the yaw error is larger than 10° , are not selected based on the direction by the vane at 78 m and the turbine yaw signal;
- We select hub-height mean wind speeds within the range 11 – 13 m s^{-1} because wind speeds above the rated value are the focus of lidar-assisted feedforward pitch control. The range is also limited to increase the number of 10-min samples;
- Because of beam obstruction from the blades, among others, the data availability of beam 3 is much lower than that of other beams and so this beam is not used in our analysis.

4.1.3. Data processing

Similar to Peña et al. [6], for each 10 min time series, we detrend the lidar LOS speed time series linearly for each measured position. Then, the spikes of the time series are removed when the values exceed ± 3 times the standard deviation of the LOS velocity within

the 10 min. Linear interpolation is lastly applied to fill the missing data.

Also, the same detrending and despiking methods in Peña et al. [6] are used to process the 1 Hz sonic and cup anemometer data. Afterwards, the sonic measurements are rotated to ensure the u component is aligned with the mean wind direction. Using the sonic anemometer measurements, the friction velocity u^* is computed as

$$u^* = (u' w'^2 + v' w'^2)^{1/4}, \tag{37}$$

where $'$ denotes the fluctuation part of the velocity component. Then, the Obukhov length [41] is calculated as

$$L_O = -\frac{u_*^3 T}{\kappa g w' \theta'_v}, \tag{38}$$

with κ being the von Kármán constant (≈ 0.40), g the gravitational acceleration, T the reference mean temperature, and θ'_v the virtual potential temperature. The Obukhov length is used later to classify our measurements into different atmospheric stability classes.

In order to assess how well the original Mann eddy lifetime expression (Equation (6)) presents the longitudinal coherence, the wind profile is needed. The second-order polynomial fit by Högström [42] is used to approximate the wind profile

$$U(z) = U_0 + A_b \ln(z) + B_a \ln^2(z), \tag{39}$$

where U_0, A_b , and B_a are three constants to be solved by least-square fitting using $U(z)$ from the cup anemometers at the height of 33, 57, and 80 m. The mean vertical shear is estimated by [43].

$$\frac{dU(z)}{dz} = \frac{A_b + 2B_a \ln(z)}{z}. \tag{40}$$

For our data, we estimate dU/dz at $z = 80$ m. We classify the 10 min periods into five atmospheric stability classes based on the dimensionless atmospheric stability parameter z/L_O , as shown by Table 2 and as similarly performed by Peña et al. [6]. $z = 67$ m is the mean height used for the stability estimates. The stability is close to neutral under class 1 and it becomes more stable the higher the class. However, there are not enough samples under unstable stability conditions and so such conditions are not analyzed in this work. For each class, the spectra of AVENT LOS velocity and those of the sonic anemometer velocity components are calculated. Then an anti-aliasing method by Kirchner [44] is applied to filter the LOS spectra from the AVENT lidar due to noise above the sampling frequency of 0.2 Hz [6]. After filtering noise, the ensemble mean LOS spectra and coherence are computed by averaging over the samples within each stability class.

4.2. Model evaluation

In this section, we compare the model based lidar spectra and

Table 2
The atmospheric flow parameters calculated from measurement data. 'No' means the number of 10 min samples.

Class	z/L_O	No	$\langle z/L_O \rangle$	$\langle U_{80\text{ m}} \rangle [\text{m s}^{-1}]$	$\langle dU/dz \rangle [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Description
stability 1	[- 0.1, 0.1)	93	0.0244	12.01	0.0195	Neutral
stability 2	[0.1, 0.2)	220	0.1514	12.26	0.0333	Near stable
stability 3	[0.2, 0.3)	133	0.2434	12.08	0.0359	Near stable
stability 4	[0.3, 0.4)	79	0.3460	12.08	0.0370	Stable
stability 5	[0.4, 0.5)	43	0.4471	11.97	0.0383	Stable

coherence against the lidar measurements from Nørrekær Enge wind farm.

4.2.1. Spectra of velocity components

We start by adjusting the Mann model of the auto-spectra of the u, v and w velocity components, and the cross-spectrum between u and w to the spectra and co-spectrum from the sonic measurements. This is achieved by least-square fitting the Mann model spectra and co-spectra via its parameters ($\alpha \epsilon^{2/3}, L$, and Γ) to the measured sonic spectra. Note that the original formulation of the eddy lifetime (Equation (6)) is used for the least-square fitting.

The fitted parameters are presented in Table 3 and the fitted and measured spectra are shown in Fig. 7. We also show the results using the Mann model adjusted formulation of τ (Equation (13)). The parameters of these adjusted τ are also presented in Table 3. As illustrated, in the stability 1 class (neutral), the τ expressions overlap with the original formulation. Modeled results are different for the other stability classes because the coherence between the LOS velocities of different beams at the same range gate are over-estimated with the original formulation of τ with increasing stability, and thus, we adjust the parameters of the shear effect related τ . For neutral conditions, the model fits well the measurements partly because the Mann model is originally formulated for shear-driven turbulence conditions.

Overall, we find good agreement between the sonic-based Mann model-based spectra and co-spectra for all stability conditions. The largest differences are found in the stable side (classes 3 to 5) for the v spectrum and the uw cross-spectrum. For stability classes 2 to 5, adjusting the τ 's slope b_1 reduces the energy of the u spectrum at low frequencies/wavenumbers mainly, which is in agreement with the sonic measurements. The turbulence length scale L decreases as the atmospheric becomes more stable, similarly to the results by Peña et al. [6,26].

4.2.2. LOS velocity spectra

After comparing the 3D turbulence spectra, we use the fitted Mann parameters to compute the model based lidar LOS auto-spectra using Equation (23). The model auto-spectra are compared with the AVENT measurements (see Fig. 8). For the stability class 1, the model based spectra are overall higher than those of the AVENT measurements, but the spectral shapes are rather similar.

For the stability classes 2 to 5, the measurements and the model agree well, especially when using the adjusted τ expressions. Within the low wavenumber range, the LOS measured spectra has a large contribution from the u component. Reducing τ 's slope b_1 mainly reduces the u spectrum within the same low wavenumber range, which results in a better comparison with the measurements.

4.2.3. Coherence with only longitudinal separation

We evaluate the longitudinal coherence from the space-time tensor Θ_{ij} using the lidar data from beam 0, because it has (only) longitudinal separations between different gates. Three gates are considered (1–3) and their coherence is shown in Fig. 9. First, we use the original eddy lifetime expression τ instead of τ_e in Equation

Table 3

The observed turbulence parameters for the space-time tensor. Fourth column onwards correspond to the adjusted parameters of the temporal-evolving τ_e . “*” means that the parameters approximate the original Mann eddy lifetime expression.

Stability class	$\alpha\epsilon^{2/3}$ [$\text{m}^{4/3} \text{s}^{-2}$]	L [m]	Γ	b_1 of τ	b_2 of τ	b_1 of τ_e	b_2 of τ_e	γ of τ [s]	γ of τ_e [s]
1	0.184	49	3.4	-1*	-2/3*	-1	-7/3	Γ	432
2	0.205	38	2.9	-0.8	-2/3	-1	-7/3	Γ	349
3	0.158	34	2.7	-0.75	-2/3	-1	-7/3	Γ	340
4	0.161	31	2.7	-0.75	-2/3	-1	-7/3	Γ	239
5	0.142	30	2.4	-0.70	-2/3	-1	-7/3	Γ	207

Fig. 7. Comparison of turbulence spectra between the model and the sonic measurements. “Model adjusted τ ” refers to adjusted slopes of τ and τ_e . “Model original τ ” refers to the original τ expression (Equation (6)) and $\tau = \tau_e$.

Fig. 8. Comparison of lidar LOS velocity spectra between the model and the Avent measurements. “Model adjusted τ ” refers to adjusted slopes of τ and τ_e . “Model original τ ” refers to the original τ expression (Equation (6)) and $\tau = \tau_e$.

Fig. 9. Comparison of LOS coherence between the model and the Avent measurements of beam 0. “Model adjusted τ ” refers to adjusted slopes of τ and τ_e . “Model original τ ” refers to the original τ expression (Equation (6)) and $\tau = \tau_e$.

Fig. 10. Comparison of LOS coherence between the model and the Avent measurement. The coherence between beam 0 and the rest beams are shown. “Model adjusted τ ” refers to the slopes of τ and τ_e . “Model original τ ” refers to the original τ expression (Equation (6)) with $\tau = \tau_e$.

(8) to account for the temporal evolution/longitudinal separation of the turbulence field. However, we observe that the LOS speed coherence by the model decays much slower than that calculated from the measurements. Therefore, we adjust the eddy lifetime τ_e so that it decays faster with increasing wavenumber. This is achieved by adjusting the slope b_2 . We find that by using $b_2 = -7/3$, there is good agreement between the coherence of the space-time tensor and the lidar measurements, as shown in Fig. 9. Apart from b_2 , the scaling factor γ also needs to be adjusted from its original

value, which is the product $\Gamma \left(\frac{dU}{dz} \right)^{-1}$ in the original eddy lifetime expression of the Mann model [15]. We list these adjusted parameters in Table 3.

By comparing Fig. 9(a)–(e), there are no considerable differences in longitudinal coherence between the investigated stability classes. The coherence decays only slightly faster in stable compared to near-neutral conditions. Within the low wavenumber range, the coherence is lower and more sensitive to longitudinal separations for stable compared to near-neutral conditions, which

Fig. 11. Comparison of LOS coherence between the model and the Avent measurement. The coherence between the beams except for beam 0 are shown. “Model adjusted τ ” refers to the slopes of τ and τ_e . “Model original τ ” refers to the original τ expression (Equation (6)) with $\tau = \tau_e$.

might caused by the smaller turbulence length scales inherent of stable conditions.

4.2.4. Coherence with lateral and vertical separations

The coherence as function of the lateral and vertical separations is now analyzed using measurements of the LOS velocities from different beam directions at the same range gate. There are also temporal delays between the LOS velocities, since the lidar does not measure at different beam directions simultaneously. However, since the delays are usually only within 1 s to few seconds, they have a lower impact in the coherence compared to that caused by the spatial separations. By using four beams (3 is not used due to low data availability), six combinations of beams are possible.

Fig. 10 shows the coherence between beam 0 and the rest of the beams. In each frame, both the coherences from gate 1 and 2 are illustrated. Generally, we see that the coherence is well predicted at gate 1 for all stability conditions and the model prediction is better the closer to the neutral class. As for gate 2, where the spatial separation is larger, the model matches the measurement for stability classes 1 to 3, but some disagreements appear under the two most stable classes. For the original τ expression and for stable conditions, the model overestimates the coherence at low wavenumbers. By adjusting the parameters in τ using the same method as for τ_e (i.e., Equation (13)), the overestimation is alleviated.

In Fig. 11, the coherence between all beams except beam 0 is illustrated. Similarly, for each frame, both the coherences from gate 1 and 2 are shown. In general, the agreement between model and measurements is much better for the neutral stability class 1 than for the rest of stability classes, although the measured coherence between beams 1 and 2 is underestimated by the model. The model predicts the coherence between beams 1 and 2 to be slightly lower than that between beams 2 and 4. However, the lidar measurements show that the coherence between beams 1 and 2 is much higher than that between beams 2 and 4. As discussed in Section 3.2, this is due to the opposite signs of the beams’ unit vector; the correlated v components on beams 1 and 2 result in decorrelation on LOS measurements between beams 1 and 2. Since the v

component auto-spectrum is well predicted by the model (when we look at the sonic spectra), it is more likely that the spatial coherence of the v component is overestimated by the model. For stability classes 2 to 5, larger discrepancies between model and measured data are found as the atmosphere becomes more stable. The modification of the original eddy lifetime of the Mann model intends to reduce these discrepancies. After applying the adjusted τ values, the overestimation of the coherence in the stability classes 2–4 is slightly reduced. However, relative large biases are still present in the last two stability classes (4 and 5) for gate 2. We can conclude that the LOS coherence decays much faster than predicted by the model when the separation becomes larger than the turbulence length scale L .

4.2.5. Coherence with separation in all directions

It is also interesting to evaluate the abilities of the space-time tensor in predicting the coherence between LOS velocities with all longitudinal, lateral, and vertical separations. Except for beam 0, the measurements at different gates along the other beams can be used for such purpose and the results are shown in Fig. 12. The model generally matches well the lidar data. Similarly to our previous coherence comparisons, the agreement between model and measurements deteriorates the more stable the atmosphere. For all stability classes, the results using the adjusted τ do not differ much to those using the original τ , because the vertical and lateral separations do not exceed the range in which the results are sensitive to the newly introduced eddy lifetime τ_e . By comparing Figs. 12 and 9, we see that the overall coherence is not that sensitive to the eddy lifetime, although there is an overestimation of the longitudinal coherence when using the original τ . The coherence decay due to lateral and vertical separations is more dominant than that due to longitudinal separations for this particular lidar beam geometry.

4.3. Rotor effective wind speed

In order to evaluate how well the space-time tensor predicts the

Fig. 12. Comparison of LOS coherence between the model and the Avent measurement. The coherence between the LOS measurements at gate 1 and 2 on different beams are shown. “Model adjusted τ ” refers to the slopes of τ and τ_e . “Model original τ ” refers to the original τ expression (Equation (6)) with $\tau = \tau_e$.

Fig. 13. Comparison of rotor effective wind speeds by the lidar and turbine.

lidar estimated REWS (u_{LL}), we use the previously adjusted model parameters (Table 3) and compare the lidar estimated REWS by the model and that derived from the Avent measurements (see Fig. 13). The single point u component spectrum by the Mann model and the model based REWS observed by the turbine are also shown. The IEA 3.4 MW reference wind turbine with a rotor diameter of 130 m is considered to calculate the turbine REWS (u_{RR}). The lidar estimated REWS is computed using the measurements from beams 0, 1, 2 and 4 at gates 1 and 2. Gate 3 is excluded because its projection onto the rotor plane is outside the rotor-swept area. The time delays according to the longitudinal separations and the mean wind speed

are applied to shift the measurements from gate 2 to have same timing as gate 1.

As shown by Fig. 13, the lidar-based REWS is well predicted by the model. The rotor acts as a spatial filter and it experiences turbulence fluctuations that are much weaker than u component fluctuations. Especially in the most stable stability class, in which the turbulence length scale is the smallest, the lateral-vertical coherence decays rapidly when the separation exceeds the length scale (see Section 4). Because the turbulence length scale is proportional to the size of the eddies with most energy and the turbine rotor is several times larger than the turbulence length scale, it is

Fig. 14. The scanning trajectory of the “rotor LOS scanner” lidar scenario.

less possible that the rotor experience coherent large eddies whose size covers the whole rotor area. Thus, the rotor spatial filtering is more noticeable the more stable the stability conditions.

5. Assessment of wind preview quality

In this section, we further use the space-time tensor to analyze the lidar wind preview qualities for the different atmospheric stability conditions and for three different lidar scenarios. Three atmospheric stability classes based on previous sections are chosen for the analysis in this section. The hub-height mean wind speed is assumed to be 12 m s^{-1} .

5.1. Three lidar scenarios

In order to clearly see the independent impacts on lidar wind preview quality by the three factors: (a) limited measurement position; (b) turbulence temporal evolution; and (c) contamination by non-longitudinal components. We consider three lidar configurations and analyze the REWSs by the lidar. And the IEA 3.4 MW reference wind turbine, which has a medium size rotor, is chosen to analyze the turbine REWS.

Firstly, the Avent five-beam lidar configuration (see Fig. 4) is

considered whose REWS is computed from three measurement gates: 72, 121, and 170 m covering 1/3 to 2/3 of the rotor radius when projected onto the rotor-swept area.

Secondly, a lidar capable of scanning the LOS wind speed within the full rotor area at 170 m upstream is assumed (namely “full LOS scanner” as shown by Fig. 14). The lidar is assumed to have a “delta function-like” weighting function so that the Fourier transform of the weighting function $\hat{\phi}(v) = 1$. Because of the dense scanning trajectory, the problem of limited measurement positions can be omitted, thus this lidar is able to reflect the impacts by non-longitudinal components contamination and turbulence evolution. Especially, when the Taylor’s frozen theory [27] is assumed, with this lidar we are able to study the impact of non-longitudinal components’ contamination. In the calculation, this lidar is realized by defining a discrete circular grid with a step size of 8 m in both y- and z-directions and the lidar scans all the discrete points at each time step. The Equations discussed in Section 2.3 are used.

Thirdly, we assume an ideal lidar, which is able to capture the u component over the rotor-swept area at 170 m upstream (see Fig. 14). The main difference to the second lidar is that the ideal lidar can be considered to have no opening angles so that it does not measure v and w components. The ideal lidar can show us the optimal filter gain (based on Equation (36)) that a lidar can reach under the evolving turbulence situation and it does not have the problems of limited measurement positions and non-longitudinal components contamination.

5.2. The impact on coherence and filter magnitude for lidar-assisted control

To study how the turbulence parameters and the turbulence evolution phenomenon influence the lidar-rotor coherence and the filter gain under different atmospheric stability conditions, we calculate the theoretical lidar-rotor coherence and the optimal transfer function magnitude by the three lidar trajectories discussed in the previous section. To show the importance of considering turbulence evolution, we also apply the Taylor’s frozen hypothesis to the first two lidar cases for comparisons. In the third ideal lidar case, we do not apply Taylor’s frozen hypothesis because

Fig. 15. The lidar-rotor coherence (a–c) and the optimal filter magnitude (d–f) of the three lidar configurations in three of five observed stability classes. See the text for the definition of the three lidar scenarios.

it simply gives a transfer function of one for all frequencies. Also, we only show the results for stability classes 1, 3 and 5 to illustrate the differences clearly.

5.2.1. The impact on coherence

The lidar-rotor coherence is shown by (a)–(c) of Fig. 15. For the Avent trajectory, we do not see much difference between considering turbulence evolution or not. However, in the rotor LOS scanner case, the coherence is way more higher than the rest and it is even higher than the ideal lidar with turbulence evolution (see the purple and blue lines). By comparing the yellow line with the green line, we also see that the non-longitudinal contamination does not influence the coherence very much when the lidar scans the full rotor swept area.

5.2.2. The impact on filter magnitude

The impact on the ideal transfer function are shown in Fig. 15(d)–(f).

We start by looking at the ideal lidar, because this indicates the maximum possible transfer function under a certain turbulence evolution condition. If Taylor's frozen hypothesis is applied, the magnitude of the transfer function is one, which is not realistic. There is only slight difference between different stability classes for the ideal lidar. In the neutral stability 1, the magnitude cross 0.6 at 0.1 Hz. While, it cross 0.7 at 0.1 Hz in the rest two more stable stability classes (3 and 5).

For the Avent five-beam trajectory, we can see that there is some space to improve the preview quality. Also, when using Taylor's frozen hypothesis, the results are similar compared to the evolving turbulence cases. This could be simply because of the limited measurement positions projected onto the rotor-swept area and because the contamination from v and w components in the LOS velocity becomes more important for the lidar wind preview compared to the impact from turbulence evolution.

In the case of the second LOS scanner lidar, the preview quality is obviously improved compared to the Avent trajectory because of the capability of scanning the full rotor area. By comparing the second lidar with the ideal lidar for the case that turbulence evolution is considered (green and yellow lines), we can see that the contamination by non-longitudinal components does not impact much the lidar preview quality. However, in the frozen case, the full LOS scanner leads to an overestimation of the preview quality (even higher than the ideal lidar), which indicates that turbulence evolution needs to be considered when a lidar is capable to scan a wide range of rotor area.

The differences within each stability class mainly appear in the low wavenumber/frequency for the Avent trajectory. In the most stable class, the turbulence length scale is smallest and more damping (lower gain) is required in the filter due to the less energy in the REWS. This is because the turbine rotor spatial filtering effect is highest, while lidar has less spatial averaging compared to the rotor due to limited measuring positions. There is no much difference in the lower wavenumber/frequency range for the full LOS scanner and the ideal lidar, because both of them have equally spatial averaging effect as the rotor.

6. Conclusions and further work

We propose a space-time tensor based on the Mann model and an eddy lifetime model. The space-time tensor describes the correlation decay of turbulence due to temporal evolution and is able to represent both the temporal and spatial structure of turbulence. A practical eddy lifetime expression is proposed, which can be adjusted to match that of the original Mann model. A numerical turbulence simulation method using the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck

process is presented and programmed as open-source software. The method allows us to generate 4D Mann turbulence fields based on the space-time tensor. The turbulence fields generated for several distances along the main wind direction are stationary 3D Mann turbulence fields. The correlation between all 3D fields is governed by the eddy lifetime model in the space-time tensor. The one at the rotor location can then be used for standard aero-elastic simulations.

The space-time tensor is evaluated using measurements from a pulsed lidar and a sonic anemometer. We classify the measurements into different atmospheric stability conditions and select periods where the mean wind speed is close to 12 m s^{-1} , i.e., periods above rated wind speed as lidar-assisted pitch forward control becomes beneficial under such conditions. We show that the model agrees well with the measured spectra and coherence from the lidar measurements. The agreement is best under neutral conditions, while there is an overestimation of coherence by the model for the most stable class, as expected. The discrepancy mainly appears in the cases where the spatial separations of LOS measurements are larger than the turbulence length scale. To alleviate such overestimation, the eddy lifetime expression in the Mann model is adjusted, which provides better agreement with the measurements.

The model also predicts the auto-spectrum of lidar estimated REWS well. In the most stable conditions, the turbulence length scale is small and smaller than the turbine rotor size; thus the filtering effect by the turbine itself is high and the resulting spectral energy of the rotor effective wind speed is low. We also analyze the impact of temporal evolution and atmospheric stability on the filter design of lidar-assisted control. For the five beam configuration we consider, we do not find a significant difference in the filter magnitude. Only small differences are found within the low frequency/wavenumber range for the number of stability classes. In the most stable atmosphere, the large spatial filtering by the rotor leads to high damping (low gain) within the low frequency/wavenumber range.

For the five-beam lidar configuration and turbulence parameters we use, assuming either Taylor's frozen hypothesis or evolving turbulence does not change much the results. This might be due to large effects of the limited measurement positions and the contamination of the non-longitudinal velocity components. When simulating a lidar with the capability of scanning a wide range of the rotor area, we show that the turbulence evolution needs to be considered to avoid the overestimation of the lidar preview quality. When we simulate a perfect lidar (i.e., one able to capture the u component over the full rotor), we obtain the limiting values of the filter gain.

In the future, the space-time tensor will be further evaluated using lidar measurements performed under unstable conditions. Also, turbines of different rotor sizes can be used to derive the REWS and validate the space-time tensor model. A detailed study on optimizing lidar scanning strategies can be performed using the space-time tensor.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Feng Guo: Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Jakob Mann:** Conceptualization, Software, Writing – review & editing. **Alfredo Peña:** Visualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **David Schlipf:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Po Wen Cheng:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

Measurements from the Nørrekær Enge site (mast

measurements and lidar) can be requested from Alfredo Peña (aldi@dtu.dk). The 4D Mann turbulence simulation tool using the space-time tensor is available from: <https://github.com/fengguoFUAS/4D-Mann-Turbulence-Generator>. From the same link, several tool codes written in Matlab are also available to visualize the simulated turbulence field.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

To comply with stationarity, we could consider the field at time $t_0 + \Delta t$ whose Gaussian complex Gaussian variables are calculated using the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process [34] (see Equation (19)). The ensemble mean of the coefficients at $t_0 + \Delta t$ is then

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle C_{ik}(\mathbf{k})g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t) [C_{jl}(\mathbf{k})g_l(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t)]^* \rangle \\ &= C_{ik}(\mathbf{k}) \langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t) \rangle C_{jl}^*(\mathbf{k}) \\ &= 2C_{ik}(\mathbf{k})C_{jk}^*(\mathbf{k}) \propto \Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}), \end{aligned} \tag{A.3}$$

since

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t) \rangle &= \left\langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0)\exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right) + g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k})\exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)\sqrt{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)} \right\rangle \\ &+ \left\langle g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_k(\mathbf{k})\exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)\sqrt{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)} + g_k(\mathbf{k})g_l^*(\mathbf{k})\left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)\right] \right\rangle \\ &= 2\delta_{kl}. \end{aligned} \tag{A.4}$$

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The derivations above could in principle be extended to any two consecutive time points, which implies that the turbulence fields of all points in time follow the Mann spectral tensor [15].

Appendix A. Proof on Using Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process for the Space-time Tensor

Appendix B. Validation of the Numerical Simulation by the Space-time Tensor

The covariances of the coefficients between t_0 and $t_0 + \Delta t$ are:

To validate the numerical simulation, 12 independent random seeds are used to generate 12 samples of 4D turbulence fields. The spectra and coherence are calculated from the fields and compared to the results by the space-time tensor, as shown by Figures B16 to B19. In each 4D field, three time moments ($t = 0, 5,$ and 12 s) are considered and the same parameters in Fig. 5 are used.

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle C_{ik}(\mathbf{k})g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0) [C_{jl}(\mathbf{k})g_l(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t)]^* \rangle \\ &= C_{ik}(\mathbf{k}) \langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t) \rangle C_{jl}^*(\mathbf{k}) \\ &= 2C_{ik}(\mathbf{k})C_{jk}^*(\mathbf{k})\exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)\Phi_{ij}(\mathbf{k}), \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0 + \Delta t) \rangle &= \left\langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}, t_0)\exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right) + g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k})\sqrt{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)} \right\rangle \\ &= 2\exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_e}\right)\delta_{kl}, \end{aligned} \tag{A.2}$$

since $\langle g_k(\mathbf{k}, t_0)g_l^*(\mathbf{k}) \rangle = 0$.

Fig. B.16. Comparison spectra of three time moments. The first point in the left-upper corner of the field is used.

Fig. B.17. Comparison of coherence with time difference.

Fig. B.18. Comparison of coherence with lateral separation.

Fig. B.19. Comparison of coherence with vertical separation.

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